

What's in a Book? A review of book-related work types in various metadata schemas, and an attempt to align these in OMP and Thoth Open Metadata

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It is a truism that the world of book publishing is far more complex than that of journals. In the context of disseminating and archiving their valuable outputs to the scholarly record, book publishers are dealing with numerous aggregator platforms and providers of PIDs, all of whom utilise a vast array of different exchange formats such as ONIX, MARC, KBART, and xml – as well as platform-specific configurations thereof.

With this presentation, we will focus on the results of a recent research project probing the differences of work type denominations across a variety of platforms and standards which has been conducted by specialists at Public Knowledge Project and Thoth Open Metadata. As we will show, this research indicates a lack of congruence across the numerous platforms and metadata standards considered, all of which offer varying degrees of granularity and specificity with regards to classifying book content.

The presentation will also provide a set of recommendations that both PKP's Open Monograph Press (OMP) and Thoth Open Metadata will take into account as vital for the further development of their respective platforms.

Context

[Thoth](#) has commissioned the creation of [a plugin for OMP](#) that will enable publishers to improve their metadata and freely generate a [variety of export formats available via Thoth](#). In doing so, they planned to map OMP's 'submission type' to Thoth's 'work type'. However, OMP includes only limited submission types, and so the two teams decided to explore the question of submission types, to see whether it may better match Thoth's evolving 'work type' taxonomy in future.

In parallel, PKP is undertaking a review of OMP, analysing the landscape and conducting user research. That work has surfaced two relevant trends:

1. There is a clear message coming from users that the system should move away from the use of 'monograph' as the default term for a publication in OMP, as most OMP users are publishing a much wider range of materials than monographs and edited volumes.

2. Some users find the limited submission types on the submission form a barrier to use as their submitting authors are contributing materials beyond the two existing categories and their presence creates confusion.

Given the shared values and goals of our two projects, we are investigating whether there is a common solution to the two identified problems.

Evaluation

Current Behaviour: Thoth Work Type

Thoth's work type is a mandatory attribute of every ['Work' record](#). The field is limited to the following options:

- [Book Chapter](#)
- [Monograph](#)
- [Edited Book](#)
- [Textbook](#)
- [Journal Issue](#)
- [Book Set](#)

The taxonomy is evolving¹, and the following are expected to be added soon:

- Report
- Thesis
- Conference Proceedings

Current Behaviour: OMP Submission Type

In the OMP interface, the submission type is selected at the time of manuscript submission, with two choices available:

1. Monograph (Authors are associated with the book as a whole.)
2. Edited volume (Authors are associated with their own chapter.)

As indicated, the existing options are essentially a binary intended to distinguish between works where each chapter has either the same, or different authors. In addition, when a user selects edited volume instead, the following variables are activated:

1. On the contributor form, a checkbox will be presented with the label "Identify this contributor as the editor of this volume" (in the OMP codebase, this is a field called "isVolumeEditor")
2. There are accommodations for licenses that are distinct for different chapters (#5338)
3. Editors assigned to the submission are listed in the chapter contributor list on published content

The submission type (monograph or edited volume) is also reflected in the import/export XML.

¹ See <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/issues/630>

OMP User Feedback

OMP users describe using the platform for many other types of content that do not fit into either of the existing submission type categories. This limitation has led at least one user interviewed to create their own submission form using Google Forms in order to offer submitting authors additional submission types, but adding complexity to their workflow in the process. In interviews, the language used to describe the materials hosted in OMP includes:

- Scientific books
- Dissertations
- Theses
- Reports
- Reference books
- Monographs
- Studies
- Series

PKP is also considering a recommendation to move away from the term monograph as the default name for a work in OMP. One of the major changes over the past decade has been the diversification of what is considered a scholarly publication, which has, if not dethroned the monograph, at least elevated other things as its peers. In order to respond and contribute to the evolving understanding of long-form scholarship, PKP is likely to update the language within the platform across the board, to replace 'monograph' as the default term with 'book', with an expanded range of submission types.

Existing Taxonomies

In order to ensure that any decisions regarding introducing new submission types in OMP are in keeping with the broader publishing ecosystem, the following is a summary of how the major metadata standards and services classify materials by type. For the purposes of this project, only the attributes that relate to the kinds of resources OMP supports, thus excluding journals, multimedia and physical artifacts.

1. [MARC](#)
 - a. 4.2.3 Type of Record: The value of the type-of-record parameter shall be an ASCII graphic character occupying character position 6 of the record.
 - b. [Type of record](#)
 - i. [BK Books](#)
 1. [Nature of Content](#): indicates whether a significant part of the item is or contains certain types of material
 - ii. [CR Continuing Resources](#)
 1. [Type of continuing content](#)
 - iii. [MX Mixed Materials](#)

1. [Form of item](#)
2. Dublin Core
 - a. **Element Name: type**
 - i. Label: Type
 - ii. Definition: The nature or genre of the resource.
 - iii. Comment: Recommended best practice is to use a controlled vocabulary such as the [DCMI Type Vocabulary \[DCMITYPE\]](#). To describe the file format, physical medium, or dimensions of the resource, use the Format element.
 - iv. [DCMI Type Vocabulary \[DCMITYPE\]](#).
 1. Collection
 2. [Text](#)
3. ONIX
 - a. List 12: [Trade category](#)
 - b. List 21: [Edition type](#)
 - c. List 51: [Product relation](#) (Part-Whole relation for edited collections and series)
 - d. List 150: [Product Form](#)
 - e. List 151: [Product Composition](#)
 - f. List 175: [Product Form Detail](#)
4. Crossref
 - a. [BookCite](#)
 - i. Book
 1. Series
 2. Content
 - ii. Dissertation
 - iii. Report
 1. Series
 2. Content
5. BITS
 - a. [Book-type attribute](#) - no guidance
6. [MODS](#):
 - [typeOfResource](#)
 - [Resource Types Scheme](#)
 - [Collection](#)
 - [Text](#)
 - [Unspecified](#)
7. [BIBFRAME](#)
 - [ContentTypes](#)
 - Text
 - Undefined
8. Schema.org
 - a. **CreativeWork**
 - i. **Book**

1. **additionalType attribute:** An additional type for the item, typically used for adding more specific types from external vocabularies in microdata syntax. This is a relationship between something and a class that the thing is in. Typically the value is a URI-identified RDF class, and in this case corresponds to the use of `rdf:type` in RDF. Text values can be used sparingly, for cases where useful information can be added without their being an appropriate schema to reference. In the case of text values, the class label should follow the [schema.org style guide](http://schema.org/style-guide).
 - ii. Chapter
 - iii. Collection
 - iv. ComicStory
 - v. DigitalDocument
 - vi. Guide
 - vii. Review
 - viii. Thesis
9. [Scientific and Technical Reports](#) (NISO)
 - a. **Element Name:** Type
 - b. **Label:** Resource Type
 - c. **Definition:** The nature or genre of the content of the resource.
 - d. **Comment:** Type includes terms describing general categories, functions, genres, or aggregation levels for content. Recommended best practice is to select a value from a controlled vocabulary (for example, the [DCMI Type Vocabulary](#)). To describe the physical or digital manifestation of the resource, use the `FORMAT` element.
10. DataCite
 - a. [ResourceTypeGeneral](#)
 - b. Comment: relevant fields include
 - i. Book
 - ii. Book Chapter
 - iii. ComputationalNotebook
 - iv. Conference Proceeding
 - v. Dissertation
 - vi. Report
 - vii. Collection (maybe?)
 - c. Comment 2: DataCite also provides suggested mappings onto Dublin Core for their work types
11. Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR) - Controlled Vocabularies for Repositories
 - a. [Resource Types](#) (see under “Concepts” on the left), with a variety of types related to books
 - b. Note that ORCID have just [recently announced](#) an expansion of their pool of supported work types, drawing on the COAR taxonomy - with “Conference Proceedings” being the most relevant to our book-related context

These findings will inform Thoth and PKP's ongoing collaboration to better align and structure our platforms' metadata. The next stage of work will involve close work with the PKP development team to scope the work necessary to change how submission types are handled in OMP, alongside other product design decisions resulting from the ongoing review work.